

Reactions of 3-Arylimino-2-Indolinones with *p*-Substituted Phenylthiosemicarbazides

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3-Arylimino-2-indolinones (II) have been prepared by the condensation of isatins (I) with anilines. Reactions of II with *p*-substituted phenylthiosemicarbazides have resulted (in every instance) in the displacement of arylimino groups by the phenylthiosemicarbazono functions.

A recent report¹ from this laboratory indicated that the 3-phenylimino group in 3-phenylimino-2-indolinone could be displaced by electron withdrawing, *p*-directing anilines. Moreover the displacement of phenylimino group also occurs with carboxylic acid hydrazides². In the present report reactions of 3-arylimino-2-indolinones (II) with arylthiosemicarbazides are described.

Isatins³ (I_a) prepared via Sandmeyer reaction were treated with anilines in ethanolic solution to yield 3-arylimino-2-indolinones¹ (II_a). When II_a were allowed to react with arylthiosemicarbazides, 3-arylimino-2-indolinones (III_a) were obtained. III_a were directly obtained from Ia and arylthiosemicarbazides. Identity of III_a obtained by both the methods was established by superimposable ir, as well as by m.p., m.m.p. and tlc. Displacement of 3-arylimino group also occurred when 1-methyl-3-arylimino-2-indolinones (II_b) were treated with arylthiosemicarbazides. III_b thus obtained were identical in every respect with the products obtained from Ib and arylthiosemicarbazides. 1-Methylisatins¹ and arylthiosemicarbazides⁴ were synthesised according to known procedures.

In this reaction the displacement of 3-arylimino-group with 3-arylimino-2-indolinone group occurred due to solubility behaviour of reactants and products. Arylthiosemicarbazides react at C-3 as a nucleophile. The intermediate products thus formed expel anilines to yield III. III so formed being sparingly soluble in the reaction medium as compared to anilines, shift the equilibrium of the reaction to the right.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infra red spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 and 177 spectrophotometer in KBr. Thin layer chromatography was done on silica-gel in benzene-ethylacetate (9:1).

3-(*p*-Substituted) phenylthiosemicarbazono-2-indolinones (III_a): From Ia: A mixture of 1.47 g of isatin (I_a), 0.01 mole of *p*-substituted phenylthiosemicarbazide and 20 ml of ethanol containing 2 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 2 hrs. The contents were cooled, filtered and washed with cold ethanol.

From II_a: A mixture of 0.01 mol of 3-arylimino-2-indolinone (II_a) and 0.01 mole of *p*-substituted phenylthiosemicarbazide was refluxed in 20 ml of ethanol for 20 mins. The contents were cooled, filtered and washed with cold ethanol.

1-Methyl-3-(*p*-substituted) phenylthiosemicarbazono-2-indolinones (III_b):

From Ib: A suspension of 1.61 g of 1-methylisatin (I_b), 0.01 mole of *p*-substituted phenylthiosemicarbazide and 20 ml of ethanol containing 2 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 2 hrs. The contents were cooled and the solid product was filtered and washed with cold ethanol.

TABLE 1—3-(*p*-SUBSTITUTED) PHENYLTHIOSEMICARBAZONO-2-INDOLINONES (III)

Comp. No.	R	R'	R''	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	NH	ir Data (in cm ⁻¹)			Tlc Rf.
							>C=O	>C=N	>C=S	
1	H	H	H	230-1	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS	3200 3300	1690	1595	1150	0.615
2	H	CH ₃	H	245-6	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS	—	—	—	—	0.923
3	H	H	Cl	238-9	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ OS	3190 3300	1690	1590	1170	0.569
4	H	CH ₃	Cl	255-6	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ OS	—	—	—	—	0.892
5	H	H	CH ₃	237-8	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS	3150 3300	1690	1600	1160	0.525
6	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	233-4	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OS	—	—	—	—	0.783
7	H	H	Br	241-3	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrN ₄ OS	3185 3300	1690	1590	1170	0.609
8	H	CH ₃	Br	245-6	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₄ OS	—	—	—	—	0.944
9	H	H	OCH ₃	237-8	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	3190 3300	1685	1610	1165	0.489
10	H	CH ₃	OCH ₃	220-1	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S	—	—	—	—	0.955
11	Cl	H	H	245-6	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ OS	3190 3310 3300	1690	1600	1160	0.655
12	Cl	CH ₃	H	245-6	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ OS	3210 3300	1690	1600	1160	0.875
13	Cl	H	Cl	234-5	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	—	—	—	—	0.512
14	Cl	CH ₃	Cl	255-6	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	3210 3300	1680	1590	1150	0.722
15	Cl	H	CH ₃	237-9	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ OS	3220 3310 3320	1690	1610	1170	0.622
16	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	233-4	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ OS	3220 3320	1690	1610	1170	0.733
17	Cl	H	Br	241-3	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrClN ₄ OS	3200 3300	1690	1610	1160	0.644
18	Cl	CH ₃	Br	245-6	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrClN ₄ OS	—	—	—	—	0.846
19	Cl	H	OCH ₃	234-5	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	—	—	—	—	0.500
20	Cl	CH ₃	OCH ₃	220-1	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	3200	1690	1595	1160	0.711

From *Iib* : 1-Methyl-3-arylimino-2-indolinone (0.01 mole) and 0.01 mole of *p*-substituted phenylthiosemicarbazide were taken in 20 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 20 mins. At the end of this period the contents were cooled and the solid mass was filtered and washed with cold ethanol.

Physical characteristics of III are recorded in Table 1.

Infrared spectra : The ir spectra of these compounds show an intense peak at about 1680-90 cm⁻¹ due to C=O stretching. Two bands were observed in compounds having ring N-H and other NH group i.e. at about 3200 and 3300 cm⁻¹ respectively. A strong peak at 1160-70 cm⁻¹ was also observed due to

>C=S stretching. >C=N stretchings were recorded around 1600 cm⁻¹.

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